

EVALUATION OF HPC STORAGE SYSTEMS FOR HEP ANALYSIS

August 2024

AUTHOR(S):

Asal Mehrabi

CERN-ROOT

SUPERVISOR(S):

Jonas Hahnfeld

Vincenzo Eduardo Padulano

ABSTRACT

While High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems are not yet critically relied upon for High-Energy Physics (HEP) analyses, their role is expected to become increasingly important in the future. This project evaluates various HPC storage solutions, with a focus on the RNTuple data format, in terms of their performance, scalability, and suitability for processing the vast amounts of data generated by particle accelerators like the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). The analysis provides insights into how HPC systems might support and enhance future HEP workflows.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	3
1.1	Introduction to RNTuple	3
1.2	High-Performance Computing Systems	3
1.2.1	LUMI	3
1.2.2	Eiger	4
1.2.3	Job Scheduling with SLURM	4
1.3	Workflow	4
1.3.1	Data Preparation	4
1.3.2	Execution	5
1.3.3	Performance Analysis	5
2	Testing and Benchmarking	6
2.1	Multithreaded analyses	6
2.1.1	Impact of Storage	6
2.1.2	Lustre Analyses	7
2.2	Analysis on Multiple Nodes	8
2.2.1	Multiple Concurrent Analyses	8
2.2.2	Comparison of Node Configurations and Concurrent Jobs	8
2.3	Multithreaded vs Distributed RDF	10
2.3.1	Implementation on HPC Systems	10
2.3.2	SLURMCluster Setup	10
2.3.3	Interactive Session on LUMI	10
2.3.4	Results and Comparison	10
3	Conclusions & Further Works	12
4	References	13

1 Introduction

Although High-Performance Computing (HPC) storage systems are not yet critical for the processing of vast datasets produced by particle accelerators like the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), their importance is expected to increase significantly as data volumes grow. The ability to manage and analyze this data effectively is vital for advancing high-energy physics (HEP) research. In this project, some HPC storage solutions are systematically evaluated to assess their performance and scalability, with a specific focus on their suitability for HEP analyses.

The primary goal of this project is to use the Analysis Grand Challenge as a benchmark for running high-energy physics (HEP) analyses on High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems, utilizing ROOT's RDataFrame with data converted into the RNTuple format. This approach is essential, as RNTuple is expected to become the primary event storage format for the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC), where it will be responsible for storing multiple exabytes of data. Successfully implementing RNTuple in this context is crucial to ensuring that HPC systems can meet the massive data processing demands of future HEP experiments, enabling them to support advanced research across the field.

1.1 Introduction to RNTuple

RNTuple is the latest data storage format developed by CERN, designed to meet the complex demands of large-scale data management in high-energy physics (HEP). Utilizing a columnar format that efficiently supports complex and nested data structures, RNTuple significantly enhances data management by enabling faster processing, optimized memory usage, and improved overall performance.

When compared to its predecessor, TTree, RNTuple introduces several key advancements that address the limitations of older storage models. While TTree is also a columnar format and has served high-energy physics (HEP) data storage needs for decades, its design does not fully leverage modern storage hardware and parallel computing capabilities. RNTuple, on the other hand, is designed with these considerations in mind, making it more suited for the increasingly complex and data-intensive workflows of future HEP experiments.

Given these advancements, it is crucial to evaluate how RNTuple performs on HPC systems, which are central to modern data-intensive applications. Assessing RNTuple's performance on HPC infrastructure will provide valuable insights into its efficiency and scalability in handling the massive data volumes expected from the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC). This evaluation is essential for ensuring that RNTuple can meet the rigorous demands of future HEP experiments and effectively manage the anticipated exabyte-scale datasets.

1.2 High-Performance Computing Systems

For this benchmarking, high-performance computing (HPC) systems were employed to evaluate the performance of data processing tasks. LUMI and Eiger were chosen as exemplary systems available during this project, with LUMI specifically selected for its flash-based storage. In this section, we examine the key characteristics of these HPC clusters and the SLURM job scheduling system used to manage and optimize computational resources.

1.2.1 LUMI

LUMI, located at CSC in Finland, is an HPC system with over 200,000 cores spread across 2048 nodes, each with 128 cores. For this project, we utilized both the LUMI flash storage

and LUMI scratch storage. The flash storage, which uses SSDs, provides faster access times compared to the scratch storage that uses spinning disks. However, due to the higher cost of SSDs, the quota on flash storage is more limited.

1.2.2 Eiger

Eiger, hosted at the CSCS in Switzerland, is another high-performance computing system, featuring around 50,000 cores, also distributed across nodes with 128 cores each. Eiger’s storage system, which is capable of managing multiple petabytes of data, integrates a parallel file system for efficient data access and high-throughput operations

1.2.3 Job Scheduling with SLURM

Both LUMI and Eiger utilize SLURM for job scheduling and resource allocation. SLURM provides efficient job scheduling, managing the scheduling of jobs across the HPC clusters. It optimizes the order and allocation of computational tasks based on resource availability and job priority. Additionally, SLURM handles resource allocation by assigning computational resources such as CPUs, memory, and storage, ensuring the efficient use of the available infrastructure.

1.3 Workflow

In this section, we will provide an overview of the workflow followed during the benchmarking process. As it is illustrated in figure 1, the workflow encompasses several key stages, starting with the initial step of gaining access to the high-performance computing (HPC) systems, followed by data preparation, execution, and performance analysis.

Figure 1: Workflow Steps

1.3.1 Data Preparation

The first step in our workflow involves preparing the data and setting up the necessary software environment. Prior to commencing the benchmarking, it is essential to become familiar with the specific configurations, node types, and resource management policies of both LUMI and Eiger. Further on, we follow the following steps:

1. Building ROOT from Source: ROOT is built from source on both HPC systems. This involved obtaining the source code from the official [GitHub repository](#), configuring the build with CMake, and compiling with 'make'. The installation is completed in the designated directory. For detailed instructions, refer to the ROOT website: [ROOT Installation Instructions](#).
2. Familiarizing with the Analysis Grand Challenge (AGC): Understanding AGC requirements and structure is crucial for aligning the benchmarking with project objectives. Detailed guidelines and datasets are available at [AGC Documentation](#).
3. Using the NanoAOD Dataset: The CMS NanoAOD Open Data is used for the benchmark which was already converted into the RNTuple format.

1.3.2 Execution

The execution phase involved submitting and managing computational jobs on the HPC systems. After preparing the environment and data, the benchmarking programs are submitted to the HPC systems (LUMI and Eiger) using SLURM. When submitting jobs, it is recommended to include the following in the bash script for launching the job:

- To ensure reproducible results, it is recommended to launch jobs using the `srun` command. In this way, `srun` provides a well controlled execution environment, improving the reproducibility for multithreaded runs.
- After some runs, we observed that job runs on LUMI and Eiger were faster on the second execution due to OS file caching and this was because cached files were accessed from memory, not from Lustre, causing inconsistent performance. The `fsync` command addresses this by telling the OS to drop files from the cache, forcing the system to read them from Lustre. This ensures consistent performance by reflecting the true I/O times.

1.3.3 Performance Analysis

Once the jobs are completed, the following steps are taken:

- Collecting Output: The output data generated from the jobs is collected from the HPC systems. This data includes the execution time which is the data we use for further analyses.
- Performance Analysis: A thorough performance analysis is conducted to assess various metrics such as processing speed, efficiency, and resource utilization to evaluate the effectiveness of the RNTuple format and the overall performance of the HPC systems.

2 Testing and Benchmarking

In this section, we conducted various analyses to evaluate the performance and characteristics of running RNTuple on high-performance computing (HPC) systems. The primary goal was to assess how well RNTuple handles large-scale data processing and to understand its efficiency and suitability for HPC environments.

2.1 Multithreaded analyses

2.1.1 Impact of Storage

In this analysis, we evaluated the impact of different storage systems on execution time and speed-up. Specifically, we compared Flash Storage and Scratch Storage from LUMI, alongside the storage system from Eiger. As mentioned before, Flash storage utilizes SSDs which offers significantly faster access times. The results, illustrated in Figure 2, show that Flash Storage delivers the best performance in terms of execution time, followed by Scratch and then the Eiger storage system.

Figure 2: Impact of Storage on Execution Time

Following this, we analyzed the speedup behavior across these three storage systems. The speed-up was calculated relative to the performance at 16 cores. The result can be seen in figure 3 and shows that all three systems scale well with the number of cores up to 64, with their speed-up closely following the ideal line. However, as we can observe, there is no significant improvement in terms of speedup after transitioning from half-node to full-node usage, indicating that the addition of more cores beyond a certain point does not yield proportional performance gains. For this reasons, in the following sections, we will delve deeper into this issue to better understand the factors contributing to it.

Figure 3: Impact of Storage on Speed-up

2.1.2 Lustre Analyses

In this analysis, we focused on optimizing execution times by adjusting the stripe count and stripe size parameters of the Lustre file system on LUMI. Striping is a technique used in the Lustre file system to distribute file data across multiple Object Storage Targets (OSTs), which can enhance I/O performance. By default, the stripe count is set to 1, meaning that data is stored on one storage server per file, and the stripe size is set to 2 MB.

Figure 4: Lustre Parameters Analysis

- Stripe Count (2): Increasing the stripe count to 2 did not result in significant improvements in execution times compared to the default configuration. The impact on performance was minimal.

- **Stripe Size (4 MB and 512 KB):** Both of these stripe size configurations demonstrated suboptimal performance, particularly as the number of cores increased. Adjusting the stripe size to either 4 MB or 512 KB led to decreased efficiency and longer execution times.

The default configuration consistently provided the best execution times across all scenarios. This was especially evident as the number of cores increased, where the default settings outperformed other configurations in terms of efficiency and speed. Therefore, these findings suggest that the default Lustre parameters are better suited for the given workload and hardware configuration than the adjusted settings. This observation is illustrated in Figure 4.

2.2 Analysis on Multiple Nodes

2.2.1 Multiple Concurrent Analyses

The primary objective of this analysis is to run multiple copies of the same analysis concurrently to simulate a multi-user environment. In this analysis, we aimed to run concurrent jobs across different numbers of nodes.

Figure 5 demonstrates the average execution times for various configurations using 128 and 64 threads on the LUMI and Eiger HPC systems. Across both thread configurations, the execution times show minimal fluctuation, indicating that performance remains relatively stable regardless of the number of nodes or tasks deployed. Notably, there is no significant improvement in execution time when transitioning from half-node to full-node configurations.

Figure 5: Multiple Concurrent Analysis for Full Node and Half Node

2.2.2 Comparison of Node Configurations and Concurrent Jobs

In this section, we conducted an analysis to understand whether there is any cache effect related to loading the dataset while running concurrent jobs. The results are illustrated in Figure 6, where various configurations were tested to observe their impact on execution time.

The key observations from this analysis are:

- **128 Threads, 1 Node:** The baseline configuration with 128 threads on a single node showed stable execution times, serving as a reference for comparing other setups.

- **64 Threads, 1 Task, 1 Node:** Reducing the thread count to 64 while maintaining a single task on one node led to a slight reduction in execution time. This indicates efficient use of resources even with fewer threads.
- **64 Threads, 2 Tasks, 1 Node:** Doubling the number of tasks on the same node resulted in a slight increase in execution time. This increase is expected as each task was running a separate copy of the analysis. Although execution time increased, the throughput of analyses doubled, which can be advantageous in a multi-user environment by allowing more analyses to be processed concurrently.
- **64 Threads, 2 Datasets:** Forcing the system to load the dataset twice with 64 threads led to a noticeable increase in execution time. This indicates that the overhead associated with loading datasets multiple times significantly impacts performance. This test was a simplification, as in a real multi-user environment, different analyses might need to load multiple datasets. Therefore, the tested scenario may not fully reflect actual conditions where multiple datasets are accessed.

These findings suggest that while performance remains relatively stable when reducing thread count or doubling tasks, introducing multiple dataset loads results in significant overhead, potentially highlighting cache effects.

Figure 6: Node Configurations and Concurrent Jobs Graph

2.3 Multithreaded vs Distributed RDF

In this section, we would like to compare the performance of Multithreaded RDF with the distributed RDF. The Multithreaded RDF is the default RDF for the AGC.

2.3.1 Implementation on HPC Systems

For this part of the project, we used Dask to distribute the workload across multiple nodes on the HPC systems. To achieve this, we integrated SLURM with Dask through the `dask_jobqueue` package ([Dask Jobqueue documentation](#)), allowing us to manage and scale the cluster dynamically based on the needs of the analysis.

2.3.2 SLURMCluster Setup

We implemented a conditional setup in the `create_dask_client` function to configure the SLURMCluster based on the target HPC system. Below is the example code for a SLURM-based cluster on LUMI:

```
if scheduler == "dask-slurm":
    cluster = SLURMCluster(
        local_directory=os.getcwd(),
        job_extra_directives=["--nodes=1", "--partition=cluster_partition"],
        n_workers=128,
        processes=128,
        account="project_number",
        cores=,
        memory="224 GB")
    cluster.scale(jobs=1)
    return Client(cluster)
```

2.3.3 Interactive Session on LUMI

Initially, we attempted to run the analysis script directly from the login nodes, but this approach did not work as expected, since worker nodes in LUMI could not connect to the scheduler process on the login node. Hence, it is necessary to request an interactive session using the `srun` command. This step is crucial because it ensures that workers can connect to the scheduler process properly. To request an interactive session, the following command should be used:

```
srun -p QUEUENAME --time=1:00:00 -N 1 --tasks-per-node=1 --pty bash -i
```

2.3.4 Results and Comparison

In our analysis, we compared the performance of multithreaded RDF execution versus distributed RDF on a single node.

We found that multithreaded execution on a single node performed better and for this specific case, distributing tasks across a single node can introduce additional overhead in terms of execution time. This observation is illustrated in the Figure 7.

Following this, we conducted another analysis (illustrated in Figure 8) where we executed a single run of the distributed RDF analysis across multiple nodes. In this setup, we found that the average execution time increased as more nodes were added, although it generally

Figure 7: Multithreaded RDF vs Distributed RDF

remained constant. This increase in execution time, despite adding more nodes, suggests that the overhead associated with network latency and inter-node communication is significant. The additional resources did not lead to a reduction in execution time due to these factors, which offset the benefits of distributing the workload across multiple nodes.

Figure 8: Distributed RDF performance for running concurrent jobs

Also, given the variability in distributed performance, it is suggested that further investigation is needed to ensure reproducibility. The results may be influenced by the dynamic nature of resource allocation and network conditions, indicating the need for more consistent testing environments.

3 Conclusions & Further Works

The analysis conducted in this project has shown that RNTuple can indeed operate efficiently on HPC storage systems, though its performance is heavily influenced by a number of critical factors. Firstly, the choice of storage parameters has a substantial impact on the overall efficiency. Fine-tuning these parameters is essential to achieving optimal execution times and making the most of the available resources.

Another significant factor is the effectiveness of resource allocation. Properly allocating computational resources, such as cores and memory, can drastically improve the performance of RNTuple, especially in multithreaded environments where parallel processing can be fully utilized.

When comparing multithreaded and distributed RDataFrame (RDF) approaches, it is evident that multithreading on a single node generally offers better performance. However, while distributed RDF shows promise for scaling across multiple nodes, it also introduces additional complexity and potential overhead. This suggests that while distributed computing can be beneficial, there is still a need for further optimization to fully realize its potential.

Looking forward, there are several areas that warrant further exploration. One of the primary goals is to test RNTuple across a variety of HPC systems beyond those currently analyzed. This will help us understand how different architectures and storage setups influence performance.

Ensuring the reproducibility of our results is another critical aspect of future work. Given the dynamic nature of HPC environments, it is important to refine our testing procedures and create more controlled conditions to minimize variability. This will help in generating more reliable and consistent results.

By focusing on these areas in future research, it is aimed to further improve the performance and reliability of RNTuple on HPC systems, contributing to more efficient and scalable data processing capabilities.

4 References

- CSC. (n.d.). *LUMI Supercomputer*. Retrieved from <https://www.csc.fi/en/lumi>
- CSCS. (n.d.). *Eiger Supercomputer*. Retrieved from <https://www.cscs.ch/computing/eiger/>
- SLURM. (n.d.). *SLURM: Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management*. Retrieved from <https://slurm.schedmd.com/>
- EPJ Web of Conferences. (2020). *Exploring high-performance computing technologies with Dask*. Retrieved from https://www.epj-conferences.org/articles/epjconf/pdf/2020/21/epjconf_chep2020_02030.pdf
- Dask Jobqueue Documentation. (n.d.). *SLURMCluster*. Retrieved from https://jobqueue.dask.org/en/latest/generated/dask_jobqueue.SLURMCluster.html

